

USSF (Uppsala model of soil structure and function): version 1.1

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1. Introduction

Soil structure regulates critical processes such as water, air and solute movement, biological activity and root growth, which directly or indirectly affect the ecosystem services provided by soil, such as crop production, carbon sequestration and climate regulation. The structure of agricultural soils is dynamic at time scales ranging from seconds (e.g. tillage and compaction) to seasons and decades (e.g. root growth and the activity of soil biota; Meurer et al., 2020a,b). Soil structure dynamics triggered by changes in external drivers (i.e. climate and soil and crop management practices) lead to feedbacks in the soil-plant system, which may result in soil physical degradation or regeneration (Henryson et al., 2018; Blanchy et al., 2023). The soil-crop model USSF (Uppsala model of Soil Structure and Function) has been developed primarily for use as an explorative tool to investigate these processes. USSF includes the most important feedbacks between soil structure dynamics, soil physical properties, hydrological processes and organic matter cycling in the soil-crop system, which affect important ecosystem services (e.g. crop growth, carbon storage) at temporal scales ranging from seasons to centuries.

The first version of the USSF model was described by Jarvis et al. (2024) and Coucheney et al. (2024). In this report, we provide a full description of version 1.1 of the USSF model. The main update to the model concerns a new module for dealing with crop residues at the soil surface.

2. Model description

2.1. Soil physical properties

Soil structure is considered in terms of the dynamics of bulk density, total porosity and pore size distribution. The connectivity of macropores is another aspect of the pore space structure that is also treated in the USSF model, albeit in a rather simple fashion.

2.1.1 Conceptual model of soil solids and pore space

The soil solids in USSF comprise mineral matter and organic matter. Both are characterized by a fixed density and thus a constant relationship between volume and mass. The mass of mineral matter is assumed to be constant in any given soil horizon, while the mass of organic matter is dynamic. The pore space in the USSF model is classified according to both origin (textural and structural pore space) and pore size, with the total porosity divided into three diameter classes, namely macroporosity, mesoporosity and microporosity, with the latter two classes comprising the matrix porosity. The structural pore space in USSF is found in all three of these size classes, while textural pore space is confined to the matrix. Macroporosity comprises three types of dynamic macropores generated by both physical (i.e. tillage, soil

shrinkage cracks; Bronswijk, 1991) and biological processes (i.e. biopores created by plant roots and soil fauna; Meurer et al., 2020a) as well as a permanent (i.e. static) macroporosity. Structural porosity in the soil matrix consists of aggregation pore space generated by microbial activity and the turnover of soil organic matter. A fundamental assumption in the USSF model is that the volume of this aggregation pore space in the mesopore and micropore pore size ranges can be expressed as a linear function of the volume of soil organic matter stored in each of these pore regions (e.g. Emerson and McGarry, 2001; Boivin et al., 2009; Meurer et al., 2020b). In addition to opening and closing soil cracks, soil shrinkage and swelling also changes the volume of the matrix pore space (e.g. Bronswijk, 1991; Boivin et al., 2009).

2.1.2 Solids and pore volumes

As a consequence of the processes generating soil structure dynamics, the thickness of a soil layer in the soil profile in USSF is variable. The thickness of a soil layer Δz [m] is given by:

$$\Delta z = \frac{V_t}{A_{xs}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{xs} is a nominal cross-sectional area of 1 m² and the total soil volume V_t [m³] is:

$$V_t = V_s + V_p = V_s + V_{mat} + V_{crack} + V_{bio} + V_{till} + V_{sta} \quad (2)$$

where V_p is the volume of pores [m³], V_s is the volume of solids [m³] and V_{mat} , V_{crack} , V_{bio} , V_{till} and V_{sta} [m³] are the volumes of soil matrix pores, cracks, biopores, tillage voids and static macropores respectively. The volume of solids in equation 2 is given by:

$$V_s = A_{xs} \left\{ \Delta z_{ref} (1 - \phi_{ref}) + \left(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}} \right) \right\} \quad (3)$$

where Δz_{ref} and ϕ_{ref} are reference values for the thickness [m] and matrix porosity [m³ m⁻³] of a fully swollen layer of mineral soil without organic matter and aggregation, M_{som} is the mass of organic matter in the layer [kg m⁻²] and γ_{som} is the density of organic matter [kg m⁻³].

2.1.3 Matrix porosity

The matrix porosity comprises both textural pore space and aggregation porosity in two size classes (i.e. micropores and mesopores) and depends on soil texture, organic matter content and swelling and shrinkage (figure 2). For the sake of simplicity, we assume a linear (or proportional) soil shrinkage characteristic of slope p , where $p = 0$ holds for rigid soils and $p = 1$ is equivalent to so-called “normal” (or basic) shrinkage (i.e. the volume shrinkage of the matrix equals the volume of water lost). Clearly, under dry conditions, this linear model will not hold, as volume shrinkage usually becomes increasingly less than the volume of water lost (e.g. Groenevelt and Grant, 2001; Stewart et al., 2016). Neglecting this “residual” shrinkage phase should not unduly affect simulations of the soil water balance, since it is normally only strongly expressed when the soil is very dry and water flow is therefore very slow. For our simple linear model, the matrix pore volume V_{mat} in equation 2 can be expressed as:

$$V_{mat} = V_{mat(ref)}(1 - p) + pV_w \quad ; \quad V_w \leq V_{mat(ref)} \quad (4)$$

$$V_{mat} = V_{mat(ref)} \quad ; \quad V_w > V_{mat(ref)}$$

where V_w is the volume of water in the soil layer [m^3] and $V_{mat(ref)}$ [m^3] is the matrix pore volume at the reference fully swollen state, which is given by:

$$V_{mat(ref)} = A_{xs} \left\{ (\Delta z_{ref} \phi_{ref}) + f_{agg} \left(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}} \right) \right\} \quad (5)$$

where f_{agg} is the so-called aggregation factor [m^3 pores m^{-3} organic matter], which determines the volume of aggregation pore space created by soil organic matter (Meurer et al., 2020b).

Combining equations 4 and 5 gives the matrix porosity ϕ_{mat} ($= V_{mat}/(A_{xs} \Delta z)$) as:

$$\phi_{mat} = \frac{\left\{ (\Delta z_{ref} \phi_{ref}) + f_{agg} \left(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}} \right) \right\} (1-p) + p \left(\frac{V_w}{A_{xs}} \right)}{\Delta z} \quad ; \quad V_w \leq V_{mat(ref)} \quad (6)$$

$$\phi_{mat} = \frac{\left\{ (\Delta z_{ref} \phi_{ref}) + f_{agg} \left(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}} \right) \right\}}{\Delta z} \quad ; \quad V_w > V_{mat(ref)}$$

We further assume that the size distribution of the textural pore space is unaffected by soil shrinkage, which means that the microporosity ϕ_{mic} [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] can be expressed as:

$$\phi_{mic} = \frac{\phi_{mat} \left\{ (f_{mic(text)} \Delta z_{ref} \phi_{ref}) + f_{agg} \left(\frac{M_{som(mic)}}{\gamma_{som}} \right) \right\}}{(\Delta z_{ref} \phi_{ref}) + f_{agg} \left(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}} \right)} \quad (7)$$

and the mesoporosity ϕ_{mes} [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] as:

$$\phi_{mes} = \phi_{mat} - \phi_{mic} \quad (8)$$

where $M_{som(mic)}$ is the store of soil organic matter [kg m^{-2}] in the micropore region and $f_{mic(text)}$ is the fraction of the textural pore space comprising micropores. USSF employs a simple empirical approach to estimate $f_{mic(text)}$, making use of the observation that the water content at wilting point is usually strongly correlated with clay content but hardly at all with organic matter content (e.g. Kätterer et al., 2006; Ostovari et al., 2015). For the Brooks-Corey water retention model employed in USSF (see section 2.2.1), we can write:

$$f_{mic(text)} = \left(\frac{\psi_{mes/mac}}{\psi_{mic/mes}} \right)^{\lambda_{mat(t)}} \quad (9)$$

where $\psi_{mes/mac}$ and $\psi_{mic/mes}$ are pressure heads [m] defining the largest diameter mesopore and micropore and $\lambda_{mat(t)}$ is the Brooks-Corey pore size distribution index for a soil consisting only of textural pore space in the matrix (i.e. without organic matter), estimated from:

$$\lambda_{mat(t)} = \frac{\log \left(\frac{\theta_w}{\phi_{ref}} \right)}{\log \left(\frac{\psi_{mes/mac}}{\psi_w} \right)} \quad (10)$$

where ψ_w [m] is the wilting point pressure head ($= -150$ m) and the corresponding water content θ_w [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] is estimated from the pedotransfer function derived by Ostovari et al. (2015) for European and North American soil data in the HYPRES and UNSODA databases:

$$q_w = 0.004 + 0.5 f_{clay} \quad (11)$$

where f_{clay} (kg kg^{-1}) is the soil clay content.

2.1.4 Crack porosity

A simple approximate expression for the volume of cracks as a function of the extent of matrix shrinkage can be derived assuming that the change of the soil layer thickness is small in relation to the initial thickness (e.g. Aitchison and Holmes, 1953; Bronswijk, 1991):

$$V_{crack} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{r_s}\right) (V_{mat(ref)} - V_{mat}) \quad (12)$$

where r_s is a dimensionless geometry factor ($1 \leq r_s \leq 3$) such that $r_s = 3$ for three-dimensional isotropic shrinkage and $r_s = 1$ for unidimensional shrinkage (i.e. subsidence). We assume here that r_s is a constant, even though it may vary with soil water content (te Brake et al., 2013).

2.1.5 Bioporosity

A phenomenological model is used in USSF to represent the generation of biopores by root decay and faunal activity (Meurer et al., 2020a) and their partial destruction by soil tillage. Note that this simple heuristic model describing the effects of macro-fauna is only appropriate for temperate climate regions where earthworms are dominant “ecosystem engineers” (Blouin et al., 2013). The change in soil bioporosity ϕ_{bio} [$m^3 m^{-3}$] ($= V_{bio}/(A_{xs}\Delta z)$) in USSF is given by:

$$\frac{d\phi_{bio}}{dt} = \left(\frac{l_r}{\Delta z \rho_r}\right) + \tau_e + \tau_a - k_{bio(loss)}\phi_{bio} - \Gamma_t f_d z^* \phi_{bio} \quad (13)$$

where l_r [$kg m^{-2} d^{-1}$] is the root decay rate (see equation 25), ρ_r is the tissue (bulk) density of roots [$kg m^{-3}$], τ_e and τ_a [$m^3 m^{-3} d^{-1}$] are the rates of bioporosity formation due to endogeic and anecic earthworms, $k_{bio(loss)}$ is a lumped first-order rate constant [d^{-1}] to account for the loss of bioporosity as a consequence of soil in-filling by various biological and physical processes (Meurer et al., 2020a), Γ_t [-] is a binary variable to indicate whether a tillage event occurs ($\Gamma_t = 1$ on the day of tillage, zero otherwise), z^* ($0 \leq z^* \leq 1$) is the proportion of the soil layer included within the cultivated layer, the depth of which can be set to different values for harrowing and ploughing, and f_d [-] is the proportion of bio-porosity lost during a tillage event.

The formation rate constants τ_e and τ_a will depend on earthworm biomass and activity, neither of which is likely to remain constant under changing agro-environmental conditions. However, rather than attempting to explicitly model earthworm populations, it seems preferable to use simpler indirect approaches to estimate their effects on macroporosity. As a more comprehensive pedotransfer scheme that could account for a wider range of the relevant factors affecting earthworm populations (e.g. soil organic matter, soil texture, bulk density, pH) is not available, we make use of a simple approach based on only one proxy variable. Thus, USSF currently assumes that the effects of endogeic earthworms vary with the soil organic matter content f_{som} [$kg kg^{-1}$] (Krück et al., 2006; Fonte et al., 2009; Eriksen-Hamel et al., 2009) expressed in the form of a threshold function:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_e &= 0 && ; && f_{som} < f_{som(c,e)} \\ \tau_e &= \tau_{e,max} \left(\frac{f_{som} - f_{som(c,e)}}{f_{som(m,e)} - f_{som(c,e)}} \right) && ; && f_{som(c,e)} \leq f_{som} < f_{som(m,e)} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_e = \tau_{e,max} \quad ; \quad f_{som} \geq f_{som(m,e)}$$

where $f_{som(c,e)}$ is a critical value of soil organic matter content and $\tau_{e,max}$ is a maximum turnover rate [d^{-1}] attained at an organic matter content of $f_{som(m,e)}$ [$kg\ kg^{-1}$]. The bioporosity generated by anecic earthworms is assumed to be determined by the mass of above-ground crop residues (Ouellet et al., 2008; Eriksen-Hamel et al., 2009), assuming a uniform distribution within the maximum depth of earthworm burrowing, z_{max} [m]:

$$\tau_a = \left(\frac{\Delta z}{z_{max}} \right) \max(\tau_{a,0}; \alpha_{bio} B_{res}) \quad (15)$$

where α_{bio} [$m^3\ m^{-3}\ d^{-1}\ (kg\ m^{-2})^{-1}$] is the rate of formation of bioporosity per mass of surface residue B_{res} [$kg\ m^{-2}$] and $\tau_{a,0}$ [$m^3\ m^{-3}\ d^{-1}$] is the minimum rate of bioporosity generated in the absence of any crop residues at the soil surface. The latter parameter is introduced to compensate for the fact that litter fall is currently not explicitly modelled in USSF and thus crop residue availability may be underestimated during the growing season.

2.1.6 Tillage porosity

A simple algorithm is used to simulate how tillage, subsequent consolidation and soil surface sealing affect the soil macroporosity in cultivated horizons. The change in the porosity of macro-voids originating from soil tillage ϕ_{till} [$m^3\ m^{-3}$] ($= V_{till}/(A_{xs}\Delta z)$) is given by:

$$\frac{d\phi_{till}}{dt} = \Gamma_t z^* \tau_{till} - (z^* k_{con} \phi_{till}) - \Gamma_0 k_{seal} ((1 - f_{int})R + C f_{int}R) \quad (16)$$

where τ_{till} [$m^3\ m^{-3}$] represents the gain of porosity due to a tillage event, k_{con} is a rate constant [d^{-1}] to account for the loss of tillage porosity due to subsequent consolidation, R is the rainfall rate [$cm\ d^{-1}$] f_{int} is the fraction of the rain intercepted by the canopy, which is approximated as a function of canopy leaf area index using Beer's law (see equation S16 in the supplementary information), Γ_0 is a binary variable indicating the uppermost soil layer (for which $\Gamma_0 = 1$, zero otherwise), k_{seal} is a rate constant for soil surface sealing [cm^{-1}] and C (-) is a factor accounting for the difference in kinetic energy between drip and throughfall due to drop diameter and velocity (Moss and Green, 1987; Nearing and Bradford, 1987):

$$C = 0 \quad ; \quad h < h_{min} \quad (17)$$

$$C = C_{max} \left(\frac{h - h_{min}}{h_{max} - h_{min}} \right) \quad ; \quad h_{min} < h \leq h_{max}$$

$$C = C_{max} \quad ; \quad h > h_{max}$$

where h [m] is the average height from which the canopy drip is generated, which is assumed to be equal to half the crop height, h_{min} [m] is a threshold above which the sealing potential of the drip throughfall becomes significant, h_{max} [m] is the height from which the velocity of the drip throughfall approaches the terminal velocity and C_{max} [-] is a weighting factor to account for larger kinetic energy at terminal velocity of canopy drip compared to throughfall due to a larger average drop diameter. The sealing rate constant, k_{seal} is assumed to depend on the organic matter content of the soil in the uppermost numerical soil layer (Le Bissonais and Arrouays, 1997; Grønsten and Børresen, 2009):

$$k_{seal} = k_{s(max)} \quad ; \quad f_{som} < f_{som(c,s)} \quad (18)$$

$$k_{seal} = k_{s(max)} \left(\frac{f_{som(n,s)} - f_{som}}{f_{som(n,s)} - f_{som(c,s)}} \right) \quad ; \quad f_{som(c,s)} \leq f_{som} \leq f_{som(n,s)}$$

$$k_{seal} = 0 \quad ; \quad f_{som} > f_{som(n,s)}$$

where $k_{s(max)}$ [cm^{-1}] is a maximum value attained when the organic matter content is less than a critical value $f_{som(c,s)}$ and $f_{som(n,s)}$ is an organic matter content above which sealing is negligible.

2.1.7 Total macroporosity and percolating macroporosity

The total macroporosity ϕ_{mac} [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] results from all processes described above:

$$\phi_{mac} = \phi_{crack} + \phi_{bio} + \phi_{till} + \phi_{sta} \quad (19)$$

where ϕ_{crack} is the crack porosity [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] and ϕ_{sta} is the permanent (static) macroporosity [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$]. Only a certain fraction of the total soil macroporosity will be long-range connected (Hunt et al., 2014; Jarvis et al., 2017). This so-called “percolating” macroporosity $\phi_{mac(p)}$ [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] influences macropore hydraulic conductivity and root growth in USSF and is given by:

$$\phi_{mac(p)} = f_{con} \phi_{mac} \quad (20)$$

where f_{con} [-] is the long-range connected fraction, which is assumed to increase linearly once a percolation threshold $\phi_{mac(t)}$ [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] is exceeded (Jarvis et al., 2017), reaching a maximum value $f_{con(max)}$ at a user-defined upper limit value of $\phi_{mac(u)}$:

$$f_{con} = 0 \quad ; \quad \phi_{mac} \leq \phi_{mac(t)} \quad (21)$$

$$f_{con} = f_{con(max)} \left(\frac{\phi_{mac} - \phi_{mac(t)}}{\phi_{mac(u)} - \phi_{mac(t)}} \right) \quad ; \quad \phi_{mac(t)} < \phi_{mac} \leq \phi_{mac(u)}$$

$$f_{con} = f_{con(max)} \quad ; \quad \phi_{mac} > \phi_{mac(u)}$$

2.1.8 Layer thicknesses and soil bulk density

Combining equations 1 to 5 with equation 12 gives the soil layer thickness as:

$$\Delta z = \frac{\{1 + f_{agg}(1 - \frac{p}{r_s})\}(\frac{M_{som}}{\gamma_{som}}) + \Delta z_{ref}\{1 - \phi_{ref}(\frac{p}{r_s})\} + \{(\frac{V_w}{A_{xs}})(\frac{p}{r_s})\}}{1 - \phi_{bio} - \phi_{till} - \phi_{sta}} \quad (22)$$

while the bulk density ρ_b [kg m^{-3}] is calculated as:

$$\rho_b = \frac{M_{som} + \{\gamma_{min}(1 - \phi_{ref})\Delta z_{ref}\}}{\Delta z} \quad (23)$$

where γ_{min} [kg m^{-3}] is the density of soil mineral matter.

2.2. Soil hydraulic functions

In USSF, soil hydraulic properties vary in time as a consequence of the changes in soil porosity and pore size distribution outlined above. The soil water retention and hydraulic conductivity functions required to solve Richards' equation for water flow in soil (see section 2.3.2) are

obtained by combining the Mualem/Brooks-Corey model (Brooks and Corey 1964; Mualem, 1976) for the soil matrix (i.e. micropores and mesopores) with the conceptually compatible model for the macropore region proposed by Jarvis (2008).

2.2.1 Soil water retention

Assuming that the residual water content is negligible, the composite soil water retention function in USSF is given by (Brooks and Corey, 1964; Jarvis, 2008):

$$\theta = \phi_{mat} \left(\frac{\psi}{\psi_{mes/mac}} \right)^{-\lambda_{mat}} \quad ; \quad \psi < \psi_{mes/mac} \quad (24)$$

$$\theta = \phi_{mat} + \phi_{mac} \left(\frac{\psi^{-\lambda_{mac}} - \psi_{mes/mac}^{-\lambda_{mac}}}{\psi_{max}^{-\lambda_{mac}} - \psi_{mes/mac}^{-\lambda_{mac}}} \right) \quad ; \quad \psi \geq \psi_{mes/mac} \quad (25)$$

where θ [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] is the volumetric water content, ψ is the soil water pressure head [m], ψ_{max} is the pressure head [cm] equivalent to the largest diameter macropore in the soil and λ_{mat} and λ_{mac} [-] are indices reflecting pore size distributions in the matrix and macropore regions. Temporal variations in the matrix porosity and its distribution between the two pore diameter classes alters the pore size distribution index in the Brooks-Corey equation (equation 24):

$$\lambda_{mat} = \frac{\log\left(\frac{\phi_{mic}}{\phi_{mat}}\right)}{\log\left(\frac{\psi_{mes/mac}}{\psi_{mic/mes}}\right)} \quad (26)$$

For the sake of simplicity, the pressure head equivalent to the largest macropore in soil ψ_{max} is assumed to be constant, while the pore size distribution index in the macropores, λ_{mac} is estimated from the soil clay content and macroporosity using the pedotransfer function derived by Jarvis (2008) from measurements of near-saturated hydraulic properties:

$$\lambda_{mac} = -1.546 + 4.2f_{clay} + 7.46\phi_{mac} \quad (27)$$

2.2.2 Soil hydraulic conductivity

Assuming that tortuosity is independent of pore size in the macropore region (Jarvis, 2008), hydraulic conductivity K [m d^{-1}] is given by:

$$K = K_{s(mat)} \left(\frac{\psi_{mes/mac}}{\psi} \right)^{2+\lambda_{mat}(2+\tau)} \quad ; \quad \psi < \psi_{mes/mac} \quad (28)$$

$$K = K_{s(mat)} + K_{s(mac)} \left(\frac{\psi^{-\lambda_{mac}-2} - \psi_{mes/mac}^{-\lambda_{mac}-2}}{\psi_{max}^{-\lambda_{mac}-2} - \psi_{mes/mac}^{-\lambda_{mac}-2}} \right) \quad ; \quad \psi \geq \psi_{mes/mac} \quad (29)$$

where τ [-] is a parameter that reflects the tortuosity and connectivity of the matrix pore space and $K_{s(mat)}$ and $K_{s(mac)}$ are the saturated hydraulic conductivities of the soil matrix and macropores respectively [m d^{-1}], given by (Jarvis et al., 1999; Jarvis, 2008; Nasta et al., 2013):

$$K_{s(mat)} = C_{mat} \phi_{mat} \left(\frac{1}{\psi_{mes/mac}^2} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda_{mat}}{\lambda_{mat}+2} \right) \quad (30)$$

$$K_{s(mac)} = C_{mac} \phi_{mac(p)} \left(\frac{|\psi_{max}|^{-\lambda_{mac}-2} - |\psi_{mes/mac}|^{-\lambda_{mac}-2}}{(|\psi_{max}|^{-\lambda_{mac}} - |\psi_{mes/mac}|^{-\lambda_{mac}}) \left(1 + \frac{2}{\lambda_{mac}}\right)} \right) \quad (31)$$

where C_{mat} and C_{mac} [$\text{m}^3 \text{day}^{-1}$] are composite constants that can be derived in principle from the underlying physical theory, which is based on a conceptual model of the soil as a bundle of capillaries. However, pore networks in soil are more complex than this model allows (Hunt et al., 2013), so in practice C_{mat} and C_{mac} should be treated as empirical coefficients.

2.3. Abiotic processes

2.3.1 Potential evapotranspiration

The Hargreaves equation, an empirical model that only needs daily air temperatures as input (Hargreaves and Samani, 1982) is used to estimate potential evapotranspiration ET_p [m d^{-1}]:

$$ET_p = 2.3 \times 10^{-6} \left(\frac{R_{ET}}{\lambda_{vap}} \right) (T_{av} + 17.8) (T_{max} - T_{min})^{0.5} \quad (32)$$

where R_{ET} is the extra-terrestrial radiation [$\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] calculated from the site latitude and the day number of the year, λ_{vap} is the latent heat of vapourization [MJ kg^{-1}] and T_{av} , T_{max} and T_{min} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] are the average, maximum and minimum daily air temperatures respectively. This potential evapotranspiration ET_p is partitioned into potential transpiration $E_{t,p}$ [m d^{-1}] and potential evaporation from the soil surface $E_{s,p}$ [m d^{-1}] and from crop residues $E_{r,p}$ [m d^{-1}]:

$$E_{t,p} = ET_p f_{int(g)} \quad (33)$$

$$E_{s,p} = ET_p (1 - f_{int}) (1 - f_{int(res)}) \quad (34)$$

$$E_{r,p} = ET_p \Gamma_w f_{int(res)} (1 - f_{int}) \quad (35)$$

where $f_{int(res)}$ [-], $f_{int(g)}$ [-] and f_{int} [-] are the fractions of solar radiation intercepted by crop residues, green leaves and the full crop canopy respectively (see sections 2.4.6 and section 2.5) and Γ_w is a binary variable that indicates whether the residues are wet (i.e. $\Gamma_w = 1$ during rainfall or snowmelt or if the soil surface is saturated, otherwise $\Gamma_w = 0$). Although surface residues reduce soil evaporation, they may also decrease net infiltration as a consequence of the evaporation of intercepted water during rain. Equations 34 and 35 show that these competing effects have been implemented in USSF by assuming that evaporation from the surface crop residue cover occurs only when they are presumed to be wet.

2.3.2 Soil water flow

Soil water flow and soil water contents in the profile are calculated with Richards' equation:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{d}{dz} \left[K \left(\frac{d(\psi+z)}{dz} \right) \right] - U \quad (36)$$

where t is time (d), z is height (m) and U [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$] is a sink term for root water uptake. The bottom boundary condition to equation 36 is specified either as a unit hydraulic gradient, which is suitable for freely drained soils with deep water tables, or as a pressure head, which is suitable for locations with relatively shallow water tables. In the latter case, the user may

either specify i.) a fixed pressure head (≤ 0) at the base of the soil profile, or ii.) a variable depth to groundwater based on minimum and maximum groundwater depths and the date of the maximum, assuming a sinusoidal variation during the year or iii.) a time-series of measured values. Note that the explicit finite difference numerical solution to equation 36 employed in USSF does not allow the simulation of saturated conditions in the soil profile either due to the presence of groundwater or “perched” water located within the soil profile that develops as a consequence of soil layers of limited hydraulic conductivity (e.g. plough pans). In the latter case, saturation in USSF is prevented and the excess water is lost instantaneously as interflow.

The upper boundary condition to equation 36 is specified as a flux q_{UBC} (m d^{-1}) determined by the difference between the evaporation rate (m d^{-1}) from the soil surface (i.e. evaporation from both surface crop residues $E_{r,a}$ and from the soil $E_{s,a}$) and the infiltration rate q_o (m d^{-1}):

$$q_{UBC} = E_{r,a} + E_{s,a} - q_o = E_{r,a} + \min(q_{max,s}; E_{s,p}) - \min(I_{cap}; R + S_m) \quad (37)$$

where $q_{max,s}$ and I_{cap} are the maximum possible flow rate [m d^{-1}] towards the soil surface and the infiltration capacity [m d^{-1}] respectively, both calculated using Darcy’s law and S_m is the rate of snowmelt [m d^{-1}]. Evaporation from crop residues $E_{r,a}$ is assumed to proceed at the potential rate $E_{r,p}$ (see equation 35) when they are wet, limited by the rate of precipitation or snowmelt or the depth of water ponded at the surface. Otherwise, $E_{r,a}$ is assumed to be zero when the surface residues are dry. Snow cover also affects evaporation from both the soil and surface residues. Potential evaporation is set to zero above a user-defined critical snow depth and is reduced for snow depths less than this critical value following a linear function.

A pond develops at the soil surface if the inflow rate from rain and snowmelt, $R + S_m$, exceeds the infiltration capacity I_{cap} . Surface runoff occurs if the depth of ponded water exceeds a maximum value, which is given as a linear function of the biomass of crop residues at the surface. An equivalent store of water in a snowpack is also modelled, with changes calculated from the difference between snowfall S_f and snowmelt S_m [m d^{-1}] given by:

$$S_f = P \quad ; \quad T \leq T_f \quad (38)$$

$$S_f = 0 \quad ; \quad T > T_f$$

$$S_m = 0 \quad ; \quad T \leq T_m \quad (39)$$

$$S_m = k_m(T - T_m) \quad ; \quad T > T_m$$

where P is the precipitation rate [m d^{-1}], T_f and T_m are limiting or threshold daily average air temperatures [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] for snowfall and snowmelt respectively, T [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] is the current air temperature estimated by interpolation from the minimum, maximum and average daily air temperatures assuming a sinusoidal variation during the day and k_m is a snowmelt coefficient [$\text{m }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$]. Finally, the rainfall rate, R , in equation 37 is thus given by:

$$R = 0 \quad ; \quad T \leq T_f \quad (40)$$

$$R = P \quad ; \quad T > T_f$$

Although daily maximum and minimum air temperatures are required by the USSF model as driving variables, the precipitation rates in equations 38 and 40 can be supplied at any time

resolution, although sub-daily resolutions (i.e. hourly) are strongly recommended. Daily precipitation data can be disaggregated to higher temporal resolutions using statistical methods (e.g. Güntner et al., 2001). This must be done externally to the model.

2.3.3 Water uptake by roots and actual transpiration

A simple physics-based model is used to calculate the rate of water uptake by roots from a soil layer U in equation 36 (de Jong van Lier et al., 2008; Jarvis, 2011):

$$U = \xi(F - F_0) \quad (41)$$

where F [$\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$] is the matric flux potential in the bulk soil ($F = \int_{\psi_w}^{\psi} K(\psi) d\psi$), F_0 [$\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$] is the matric flux potential at the soil/root interface and ξ is a composite root parameter [m^{-2}] given by (de Jong van Lier et al., 2008):

$$\xi = \frac{4}{r_o^2 - a^2 r_m^2 + 2(r_o^2 + r_m^2) \text{LN}\left(\frac{a r_m^2}{r_o^2}\right)} \quad (42)$$

where r_o [m] is the root radius, a is the distance to the root (normalized by r_m) at which the water content is equal to the average value in the layer (which is fixed here at 0.53; de Jong van Lier et al., 2008) and r_m [m] is the average half distance to the root surface calculated as:

$$r_m = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi R_{LD}}} \quad (43)$$

where R_{LD} (m m^{-3}) is the effective root length density in the soil layer given by:

$$R_{LD} = \varepsilon_{r(max)} f_a \left(\frac{B_{root}}{\Delta z} \right) S_{root} \quad (44)$$

where B_{root} [kg m^{-2}] is the root biomass in the soil layer (see section 2.4.5), $\varepsilon_{r(max)}$ is the maximum effective root fraction, f_a [-] is an aeration stress index (see section 2.4.7.1) and S_{root} [m kg^{-1}] is the specific root length.

Neglecting water storage changes in the plants, the actual transpiration rate $E_{t,a}$ (m d^{-1}) is calculated as the minimum of the potential transpiration rate and the maximum possible flow rate of water to the crop rooting system, $q_{max,r}$ (m d^{-1}):

$$E_{t,a} = \min(q_{max,r}; E_{t,p}) \quad (45)$$

where $q_{max,r}$ is obtained by integrating equation 41 with $F_0 = 0$ across the entire root zone. F_0 in equation 41 is then given by:

$$F_0 = \frac{q_{max,r} - E_{t,p}}{\sum \rho \Delta z} \quad ; \quad q_{max,r} \geq E_{t,p} \quad (46)$$

$$F_0 = 0 \quad ; \quad q_{max,r} < E_{t,p}$$

It can be seen from the above equations that crop water stress develops earlier when potential transpiration rates are high and total effective root length density is small (Jarvis, 2011).

2.3.4 Soil temperatures

In the USSF model, soil temperatures T_s [°C] are calculated by the heat conduction equation:

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ D_{soil} \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial z} \right) \right\} \quad (47)$$

where D_{soil} is the soil thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$) given by:

$$D_{soil} = \left(\frac{k_h}{C_h} \right) \quad (48)$$

where C_h is the thermal capacity ($\text{J m}^{-3} \text{°C}^{-1}$) estimated from:

$$C_h = (4.2 \times 10^6 \theta) + \{(1 - \phi_{mat} - \phi_{mac}) w_{min}\} \quad (49)$$

where w_{min} is a weighted heat capacity of the soil solids [$\text{J m}^{-3} \text{°C}^{-1}$] given by:

$$w_{min} = 2.7 \times 10^6 f_{som} + 2 \times 10^6 (1 - f_{som}) \quad (50)$$

and k_h is the thermal conductivity ($\text{J m}^{-1} \text{°C}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) estimated from:

$$k_h = 86400 \left\{ A1 + A2 \exp \left(\frac{-A3}{1000\theta} \right) \right\} \quad (51)$$

where the empirical constants $A1$, $A2$ and $A3$ are given by (Hubrechts, 1998):

$$A1 = -0.295 + 1.26 f_{clay} + 0.388 \gamma_b \quad (52)$$

$$A2 = -1.766 + 6.2 f_{som} + 2.0476 \gamma_b \quad (53)$$

$$A3 = \exp(0.976 + 6.5 f_{clay} + 7 f_{som}) \quad (54)$$

The bottom boundary condition needed to solve equation 47 is given by an analytical solution of equation 47 that assumes a sinusoidal variation of temperature during the year and requires user-specified estimates of mean January and July air temperatures and the so-called “damping depth”. The upper boundary condition is given by the soil surface temperature T_{surf} [°C], which is approximated from a weighted average of the current air temperature T [°C] and the temperature at the mid-point of the uppermost soil layer $T_{s,1}$ [°C], accounting for the presence of a snowpack and/or surface crop residues:

$$T_{surf} = \frac{(D_{soil} D_{snow} z_{res}^2 + D_{soil} D_{res} z_{snow}^2) T_{s,1} + D_{res} D_{snow} \frac{\Delta z_1^2}{2} T}{D_{soil} D_{snow} z_{res}^2 + D_{soil} D_{res} z_{snow}^2 + D_{res} D_{snow} \frac{\Delta z_1^2}{2}} \quad (55)$$

where D_{snow} and D_{res} [$\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$] are the thermal diffusivities of the snow and crop residues respectively, Δz_1 is the thickness of the uppermost soil layer and z_{snow} and z_{res} [m] are the thicknesses of the snow and crop residue layers. Note that when the soil surface is covered neither by snow nor crop residues (i.e. $z_{snow} = z_{res} = 0$), this simplifies to:

$$T_{surf} = T \quad (56)$$

2.4. Crop growth

2.4.1 Assimilation

Assimilation, A ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) is calculated from incoming solar radiation R_s [$\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$]:

$$A = f_{int(g)} R_s RUE_{max} f_{t(a)} f_{w(a)} \quad (57)$$

where RUE_{max} is the maximum radiation use efficiency [kg MJ^{-1}], $f_{int(g)}$ is the fraction [-] of R_s intercepted by the living crop canopy, which depends on the green leaf area index according to Beer's law (see section 2.4.6) and $f_{t(a)}$ and $f_{w(a)}$ are two dimensionless stress functions, varying between zero and unity, to represent the effects of temperature and water stress on dry matter production (see section 2.4.7, equations 77 and 79 respectively).

2.4.2 Crop development stages

Following some existing crop models (e.g. Berghuijs et al., 2020), the allocation of dry matter among four biomass components (leaves, stems, grain and roots) is calculated as a function of the crop development stage, S_d [-], which depends on daylength and temperature:

$$\begin{aligned} S_d &= 0 & ; & \quad T_{sum} \leq T_{sum(e)} & (58) \\ S_d &= \left(\frac{T_{sum} - T_{sum(e)}}{T_{sum(a)} - T_{sum(e)}} \right) & ; & \quad T_{sum(e)} < T_{sum} \leq T_{sum(a)} \\ S_d &= 1 + \left(\frac{T_{sum} - T_{sum(a)}}{T_{sum(m)} - T_{sum(a)}} \right) & ; & \quad T_{sum(a)} < T_{sum} \leq T_{sum(m)} \\ S_d &= 2 & ; & \quad T_{sum} > T_{sum(m)} \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{sum(e)}$, $T_{sum(a)}$ and $T_{sum(m)}$ are temperature sums [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] required after sowing to reach crop emergence, anthesis and maturity and the temperature sum T_{sum} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] is calculated as:

$$T_{sum} = \sum \left(\max \left(0; \left(\min(T_{av}; T_{cap}) - T_b \right) \right) f_{vern} f_{photo} \right) \quad (59)$$

where T_b and T_{cap} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] are base and ceiling temperatures respectively and f_{vern} and f_{photo} [-] are factors varying from zero to one included to account for the vernalization requirement of winter crops and the photoperiod effect respectively. The functions used in USSF for f_{vern} and f_{photo} are the same as those in the WOFOST model, as described in Ceglar et al. (2019). Note that it is assumed that only temperature affects T_{sum} between sowing and emergence. The temperature sum is accumulated from the date of sowing and reset to zero at crop harvest.

2.4.3 Allocation

The growing season is divided into five periods at four values of the crop development stage S_d (S_{d1} to S_{d4}). Partitioning of dry matter varies among these growth periods, with leaves and roots prioritized early in the season and grain-filling at the end (see figure S1). The fraction allocated to below-ground production, f_{bg} , is calculated first, as the minimum of a demand for assimilates $A_{bg(d)}$ [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] and the potential supply:

$$f_{bg} = \left(\frac{\min(A_{bg(d)}; A f_{bg(max)})}{A} \right) \quad (60)$$

where $f_{bg(max)}$ [-] is the maximum fraction of assimilates allocated to below-ground production which is assumed to depend on the crop development stage:

$$f_{bg(max)} = f_{bg(max,e)} \quad ; \quad S_d \leq S_{d1} \quad (61)$$

$$f_{bg(max)} = f_{bg(max,e)} - (f_{bg(max,e)} - f_{bg(max,l)}) \left(\frac{S_d - S_{d1}}{S_{d3} - S_{d1}} \right) \quad ; \quad S_{d1} < S_d \leq S_{d3}$$

$$f_{bg(max)} = f_{bg(max,l)} \quad ; \quad S_d > S_{d3}$$

where $f_{bg(max,e)}$ and $f_{bg(max,l)}$ are maximum allocation fractions [-] at early and late growing season periods respectively. The below-ground demand for assimilates in equation 60 is assumed to be proportional to the root biomass B_{root} [kg m⁻²] in each layer i modified by functions representing the effects of aeration f_a , soil strength f_s and soil temperature $f_{t,r}$:

$$A_{bg(d)} = R_{bg(pot)} \sum_i B_{root} f_a f_s f_{t,r} \quad (62)$$

where $R_{bg(pot)}$ is a first-order rate coefficient [d⁻¹]. Once assimilates have been allocated to the roots, the fraction of dry matter partitioned to grain f_{grain} [-] is given by (figure S1):

$$f_{grain} = 0 \quad ; \quad S_d \leq S_{d3} \quad (63)$$

$$f_{grain} = \left(\frac{S_d - S_{d3}}{S_{d4} - S_{d3}} \right) (1 - f_{bg}) \quad ; \quad S_{d3} < S_d \leq S_{d4}$$

$$f_{grain} = (1 - f_{bg}) \quad ; \quad S_d > S_{d4}$$

while the fraction allocated to leaves f_{leaf} [-] is calculated as:

$$f_{leaf} = f_{leaf(max)} (1 - f_{bg}) \quad ; \quad S_d \leq S_{d1} \quad (64)$$

$$f_{leaf} = \left\{ f_{leaf(max)} - f_{leaf(max)} \left(\frac{S_d - S_{d1}}{S_{d2} - S_{d1}} \right) \right\} (1 - f_{bg}) \quad ; \quad S_{d1} < S_d \leq S_{d2}$$

$$f_{leaf} = 0 \quad ; \quad S_d > S_{d2}$$

where $f_{leaf(max)}$ [-] is the maximum fraction of DM allocated to the leaves. The remaining dry matter is then partitioned to the stem biomass:

$$f_{stem} = 1 - f_{leaf} - f_{grain} - f_{bg} \quad (65)$$

Figure 1. Dry matter allocation as a function of crop development stage, S_d ($S_{d1} = 0.3$; $S_{d2} = 0.8$; $S_{d3} = 1.0$; $S_{d4} = 1.8$; $f_{bg(max,e)} = 0.35$; $f_{bg(max,l)} = 0$; $f_{leaf(max)} = 0.5$). From Jarvis et al. (2024).

2.4.4 Above-ground growth

Changes of dry matter in four above-ground crop components (i.e. grain, stem, green leaf and dead leaf biomass, B_{grain} , B_{stem} , $B_{leaf(g)}$, $B_{leaf(d)}$) [kg m^{-2}] are given by:

$$\frac{dB_{grain}}{dt} = f_{grain}A + \Gamma_{d3}k_{tr}B_{stem} + \Gamma_{d2}f_{tr}k_{sen}B_{leaf(g)} - \Gamma_h B_{grain} \quad (66a)$$

$$\frac{dB_{stem}}{dt} = f_{stem}A - \Gamma_{d3}k_{tr}B_{stem} - \Gamma_h B_{stem} \quad (66b)$$

$$\frac{dB_{leaf(g)}}{dt} = f_{leaf}A - \Gamma_{d2}k_{sen}B_{leaf(g)} - \Gamma_h B_{leaf(g)} \quad (66c)$$

$$\frac{dB_{leaf(d)}}{dt} = \Gamma_{d2}(1 - f_{tr})k_{sen}B_{leaf(g)} - \Gamma_h B_{leaf(d)} \quad (66d)$$

where Γ_h is a binary variable (zero or unity) indicating harvest (1 else 0), k_{tr} is a rate constant [d^{-1}] that determines the rate of transfer of reserves stored in the stem to the grain, Γ_{d3} is a binary variable that is used to indicate whether development stage S_{d3} has been reached (in which case $\Gamma_{d3} = 1$, otherwise $\Gamma_{d3} = 0$), f_{tr} [-] is the fraction of the green leaf biomass lost by senescence that is transferred to the grain, Γ_{d2} is a binary variable used to indicate whether development stage S_{d2} has been reached (in which case $\Gamma_{d2} = 1$, otherwise $\Gamma_{d2} = 0$), while k_{sen} [d^{-1}] is a coefficient determining the rate of senescence of green leaf biomass:

$$k_{sen} = k_{sen(min)} + (k_{sen(max)} - k_{sen(min)})\max(1 - f_{t(s)}; 1 - f_{w(s)}) \quad (67)$$

where $k_{sen(max)}$ and $k_{sen(min)}$ [d^{-1}] are maximum and minimum values of the senescence rate coefficient, and $f_{w(s)}$ and $f_{t(s)}$ are dimensionless stress functions [-] that enhance the rate of senescence under water stress and for sub-optimal air temperatures (equations 78 and 79).

A comparison of equation 66a-d with equations 63 and 64 shows that translocation from stem reserves to grain is assumed to start once assimilates are also used for grain-filling, while leaf

senescence only occurs once allocation to leaf biomass has ceased. Finally, it can be noted that a user-defined proportion of the leaf and stem biomass is removed at harvest, while the remainder is left on the soil surface as above-ground residues.

2.4.5 Below-ground production and root growth

A diffusion model is employed in USSF to mimic root growth and the downward penetration of roots in the soil (e.g. Page and Gerwitz, 1974; Dathe et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2021) with changes in root biomass B_{root} [kg m⁻²] in a soil layer given by:

$$\frac{\partial B_{root}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(D \left(\frac{\partial B_{root}}{\partial z} \right) \right) - I_r \quad (68)$$

where D is the root diffusion coefficient [m² d⁻¹] and I_r is the root decay rate [kg m⁻² d⁻¹], which is assumed to be negligible when the plants are young:

$$I_r = (k_d(1 - \Gamma_h) \Gamma_{d1} + \Gamma_h) B_{root} \quad (69)$$

where k_d is a rate constant for root decay during the growing season [d⁻¹] and Γ_{d1} indicates that the crop development stage is later than S_{d1} ($\Gamma_{d1} = 1$, zero otherwise). The lower boundary condition to equation 68 is specified as a zero flux, while the upper boundary condition is specified as the supply rate of assimilates from above-ground that is available to be utilized for root growth A_{roots} [kg m⁻² d⁻¹], which is given by:

$$A_{roots} = A f_{bg}(1 - f_{ex}) \quad (70)$$

where f_{ex} [-] is a fraction of the below-ground production which is directly input to the soil as root exudates and therefore does not contribute to root growth. The diffusion coefficient D for root penetration in the profile in equation 68 depends on soil temperature, soil strength and the crop development stage, with no root elongation at later stages. Following Gaiser et al. (2013), we modify the soil strength factor f_s (see equations 80 and 81) to reflect the ability of roots to by-pass mechanically strong soil by growing through connected soil macropores:

$$D = (1 - \Gamma_{d3}) D_{max} f_{t,r} \{ f_s + (1 - f_s) f_{con} \} \quad (71)$$

where D_{max} [m² d⁻¹] is the maximum value of the root diffusion coefficient. Equations 62 and 71 show that although connected macroporosity may allow roots to penetrate downwards in the profile at maximum rates in the USSF model, it is assumed that they do not alleviate reductions in the below-ground demand for assimilates in mechanically strong soil.

2.4.6 Radiation interception

Assuming that dead leaves do not shade green leaves, the fraction of radiation intercepted by the green leaves of the crop (see equation 57) can be estimated from Beer's law:

$$f_{int(g)} = 1 - e^{-\beta GLAI} \quad (72)$$

where GLAI is the green leaf area index given by:

$$GLAI = B_{leaf(g)} S_{leaf} \quad (73)$$

where S_{leaf} [$m^2 kg^{-1}$] is the specific leaf area and β [-] is the extinction coefficient. An option is available in the USSF model to consider the extinction coefficient as a variable (e.g. Zhang et al., 2014), with β calculated as a bi-linear function of the total leaf area index, LAI:

$$\beta = \beta_2 + (\beta_1 - \beta_2) \left(\frac{LAI_b - LAI}{LAI_b} \right) \quad ; \quad LAI < LAI_b \quad (74)$$

$$\beta = \beta_2 \quad ; \quad LAI \geq LAI_b$$

where β_1 is the value of the extinction coefficient at crop emergence and β_2 is the value for leaf area indices larger than LAI_b .

The fraction of radiation intercepted by the total canopy biomass, f_{int} [-], is calculated using equation 72, but with GLAI replaced by the total leaf area index, LAI [$m^2 m^{-2}$], given by:

$$LAI = (B_{leaf(g)} + B_{leaf(a)}) S_{leaf} \quad (75)$$

2.4.7 Stress factors affecting crop growth

The stress functions used to modify above- and below-ground growth in USSF for sub-optimal water status (both waterlogging and drought stress), temperature and mechanical impedance (soil strength) are described in the following sections.

2.4.7.1 Aeration stress

A simple threshold function is used to characterize the deleterious effects of anaerobic conditions on root growth (equation 62) and water uptake by roots via the effective root fraction in a soil layer (equation 44):

$$f_a = \left(\frac{\theta_a}{\theta_{a(crit)}} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_a \leq \theta_{a(crit)} \quad (76)$$

$$f_a = 1 \quad ; \quad \theta_a > \theta_{a(crit)}$$

where θ_a and $\theta_{a(crit)}$ [$m^3 m^{-3}$] are the volumetric air content and a critical value of the air content below which aeration stress occurs respectively.

2.4.7.2 Water stress

As in many other models of crop growth, USSF uses the ratio of actual to potential transpiration to represent the effects of water stress on assimilation:

$$f_{w(a)} = \frac{E_{t,a}}{E_{t,p}} \quad (77)$$

A second water stress index is defined that regulates leaf senescence in the model ($f_{w(s)}$ in equation 67). This index varies between zero and unity as a threshold function of the matric flux potential at the root surface F_o calculated in USSF using the model described by de Jong van Lier (2008) (see equations 41 to 46):

$$f_{w(s)} = 1 \quad ; \quad F_o \geq F_{o(crit)} \quad (78)$$

$$f_{w(s)} = \frac{F_o}{F_{o(crit)}} \quad ; \quad F_o < F_{o(crit)}$$

where $F_{o(crit)}$ is a critical value of F_o , which is in turn calculated from a user-defined value of a critical pressure head at the soil/root interface, $\psi_{o(crit)}$.

2.4.7.3 Temperature stress

The effect of temperature on assimilation (equation 57) and leaf senescence (equation 67) is modelled with a piece-wise linear function:

$$f_{t(s,a)} = 0 \quad ; \quad T_{av} < T_b \text{ or } T_{av} > T_c \quad (79)$$

$$f_{t(s,a)} = \left(\frac{T_{av} - T_b}{T_{o(low)} - T_b} \right) \quad ; \quad T_b \leq T_{av} \leq T_{o(low)}$$

$$f_{t(s,a)} = \left(\frac{T_c - T_{av}}{T_c - T_{o(high)}} \right) \quad ; \quad T_{o(high)} \leq T_{av} \leq T_c$$

$$f_{t(s,a)} = 1 \quad ; \quad T \geq T_{o(low)} \text{ and } T \leq T_{o(high)}$$

where $T_{o(low)}$ and $T_{o(high)}$ [°C] define an optimum temperature range and T_c [°C] is a upper temperature [°C] at which the function is zero. The same function is also used to modify root biomass growth and elongation rate (equations 62 and 71), but in this case the mean air temperature T_{av} is replaced by the soil temperature T_s .

2.5.7.4 Soil strength

The soil strength factor f_s controlling root growth in soil (equations 62 and 71) is calculated from soil water potential, soil depth and bulk density making use of the pedotransfer function for penetration resistance Q [kPa] developed by Gao et al. (2016):

$$Q = \omega \left(\left(\frac{(F-e)^2}{(1+e)} \right) (\sigma^b - \psi S^*)^f \right)^2 \quad (80)$$

where ω is the product of bulk density (expressed in g cm^{-3}) and the gravitational force ($= 9.81 \text{ N kg}^{-1}$), e is the void ratio, σ is overburden pressure (kPa), ψ is the pressure potential expressed in kPa, S^* equals either the degree of saturation or 0.5, whichever is the larger, while b , F and f are fitting parameters. The soil strength factor f_s is given as a bi-linear function of Q :

$$f_s = 1 \quad ; \quad Q \leq Q_{opt} \quad (81)$$

$$f_s = 1 - \left(\frac{Q - Q_{opt}}{Q_{lim} - Q_{opt}} \right) \quad ; \quad Q_{opt} < Q \leq Q_{lim}$$

$$f_s = 0 \quad ; \quad Q > Q_{lim}$$

where Q_{lim} defines a penetration resistance that completely stops root growth into the soil matrix, while penetration resistances less than Q_{opt} do not limit root growth at all.

2.5. Crop residues at the soil surface

The change in surface residue biomass B_{res} [kg m^{-2}] is given by:

$$\frac{dB_{res}}{dt} = \left((1 - f_{export}) \Gamma_h B_{ag} \right) - (k_{res} k_{t(res)} B_{res}) - (\Gamma_t B_{res}) \quad (82)$$

where B_{ag} [kg m⁻²] is the mass of above-ground residues at harvest, f_{export} [-] is the fraction of residues exported at harvest, k_{res} [d⁻¹] is a lumped first-order rate constant for the loss of residue biomass by both faunal incorporation and decomposition and $k_{t(res)}$ [-] is a temperature response function regulating the rate of loss of crop residues:

$$k_{t(res)} = MIN \left(1; \left(\frac{MAX(0; T_{av})}{T_{opt(res)}} \right)^2 \right) \quad (83)$$

where $T_{opt(res)}$ [°C] is an optimum temperature.

The thickness of the crop residue layer at the soil surface affects soil temperatures by determining the surface boundary condition for heat flow. The residue thickness z_{res} [m] is calculated assuming a constant residue bulk density r_{res} [kg m⁻³] (Gonzalez-Sosa et al., 2001):

$$z_{res} = \frac{B_{res}}{\rho_{res}} \quad (84)$$

Surface residues also provide cover for the soil surface through shading and a greater aerodynamic resistance for vapour flow, thereby reducing potential evaporation. The fraction of the soil surface covered by crop residues $f_{int(res)}$ [-] is given by:

$$f_{int(res)} = \min \left(1, \frac{B_{res}}{B_{crit}} \right) \quad (85)$$

where B_{crit} [kg m⁻²] is a critical crop residue mass, when complete soil cover is reached.

2.6. Soil organic matter storage and turnover

The SOM module in USSF is based on the dual-porosity version of the ICBM model (Andrn and Ktterer, 1997) described by Meurer et al. (2020b) and further developed by Coucheney et al. (2024). The model tracks four pools of organic matter in soil, two pools of younger particulate OM (subscript ‘‘Y’’) and two pools of old microbially-processed OM (subscript ‘‘O’’). For both types of OM, one part is stored in microporous regions of the soil where it is partially protected from decomposition (e.g. Ekschmitt et al., 2008; Dungait et al., 2012; Kravchenko and Guber, 2017), while the remainder is stored in regions of the soil in contact with larger mesopores, which facilitates faster decomposition. Soil structure also affects OM inputs to the soil. In order to account for spatial variations in root growth in soil, the partitioning of organic matter derived from both root decay and root exudation between micropore and mesopore regions of the soil is affected by their relative volumes as well as by soil mechanical strength.

The total mass of organic matter in a soil layer [kg m⁻²] is:

$$M_{som} = M_{Y(mes)} + M_{O(mes)} + M_{Y(mic)} + M_{O(mic)} \quad (86)$$

where changes in the mass of SOM in the four pools [kg m⁻²] are given by:

$$\frac{dM_{Y(mes)}}{dt} = I_a + \left\{ (1 - f_{r(mic)}) (I_r + f_{bg} A f_r f_{ex}) \right\} - k_Y k_t k_w k_u(mes) M_{Y(mes)} + T_Y \quad (87)$$

$$\frac{dM_{O(mes)}}{dt} = (\varepsilon k_Y k_t k_w k_u(mes) M_{Y(mes)}) - ((1 - \varepsilon) k_O k_t k_w k_u(mes) M_{O(mes)}) + T_O \quad (88)$$

$$\frac{dM_{Y(mic)}}{dt} = f_{r(mic)}(I_r + f_{bg}A f_r f_{ex}) - k_Y k_t k_w k_{u(mic)} F_p M_{Y(mic)} - T_Y \quad (89)$$

$$\frac{dM_{O(mic)}}{dt} = (\varepsilon k_Y k_t k_w k_{u(mic)} F_p M_{Y(mic)}) - ((1 - \varepsilon) k_O k_t k_w k_{u(mic)} F_p M_{O(mic)}) - T_O \quad (90)$$

where I_a , [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] is the supply of organic matter to the layer in question from incorporated above-ground harvest residues and organic amendments, $f_{r(mic)}$ is the fraction [-] of root-derived OM which is input to the micropore region, f_r [-] is the fraction of the root biomass in the soil layer, ε [-] is the organic matter retention coefficient, k_Y and k_O [d^{-1}] are reference first-order rate constants for the decomposition of young and old organic matter, F_p [-] is a factor varying from zero to unity that reduces OM decomposition rates in the micropore region to account for physical protection, $k_{u(mes)}$ and $k_{u(mic)}$ [-] are microbial uptake factors, k_t is a temperature response function [-] given by (Ratkowsky et al., 1982; Kätterer et al., 1998):

$$k_t = \frac{(T_s - T_0)^2}{(T_{ref} - T_0)^2} \quad ; \quad T_s \geq T_0 \quad (91)$$

$$k_t = 0 \quad ; \quad T_s < T_0$$

where T_{ref} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) is a reference temperature and T_0 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) is the temperature at which the mineralization of soil organic matter ceases, and k_w [-] is a moisture response function. Two alternative functions are available in the USSF model, both of which aim to reflect the effects of oxygen and solute diffusion rates on decomposition rates of organic matter. The first approach is derived from equations presented in Moyano et al. (2013):

$$k_w = 0 \quad ; \quad \theta \leq \theta_{crit}$$

$$k_w = \left[\frac{4(f - \theta - \theta_{a(crit)})(\theta - \theta_{crit})}{(\phi - \theta_{crit} - \theta_{a(crit)})^2} \right]^{n_w} \quad ; \quad \theta_{crit} < \theta \leq \phi - \theta_{a(crit)} \quad (92)$$

$$k_w = 0 \quad ; \quad \theta > \phi - \theta_{a(crit)}$$

where ϕ ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$) is the total porosity ($= \phi_{mat} + \phi_{mac}$), θ_{crit} ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$) is a critical water content at which soil organic matter mineralization is zero because of a breakdown in continuity of the water phase and n_w is an exponent which should take values of ca. 2 to 3 (Moyano et al., 2013). Equation 92 predicts that the optimum soil moisture conditions for SOM decomposition occur at a degree of saturation in the soil ($= \theta/\phi$) of $0.5 + \{(\theta_{crit} - \theta_{a(crit)})/2\}$ (Moyano et al., 2013). The second approach is an empirical piece-wise linear function based on laboratory data on CO_2 emissions from soils of intact structure (Coucheney et al., 2025; Widanagamage et al., 2025):

$$k_w = 0 \quad ; \quad q \leq \theta_{crit}$$

$$k_w = f_{sat(mic)} \left(\frac{\theta - \theta_{crit}}{\phi_{mic} - \theta_{crit}} \right) \quad ; \quad \theta_{crit} < \theta \leq \phi_{mic} \quad (93)$$

$$k_w = f_{sat(mic)} + \left\{ (1 - f_{sat(mic)}) \left(\frac{\theta - \phi_{mic}}{\phi - \theta_{a(crit)} - \phi_{mic}} \right) \right\} \quad ; \quad \phi_{mic} < \theta \leq \phi - \theta_{a(crit)}$$

$$k_w = 1 - \left\{ (1 - f_{sat}) \left(\frac{\theta - \phi + \theta_{a(crit)}}{\theta_{a(crit)}} \right) \right\} \quad ; \quad \phi - \theta_{a(crit)} < \theta$$

where $f_{sat(mic)}$ and f_{sat} are the values of the response function at micropore saturation and full saturation respectively. In this model, the optimum degree of saturation for organic matter decomposition is $1 - (\theta_{a(crit)}/\phi)$ (i.e. much closer to saturation than is the case for equation 92).

The microbial uptake limitation factors $k_{u(mes)}$ and $k_{u(mic)}$ in equations 87 to 90 are introduced to implicitly account for the dynamic effects of the microbial biomass on OM decomposition rates (i.e. positive and negative priming). They were derived by Wutzler and Reichstein (2013) from a quasi-steady-state solution to a model of microbial growth and carbon decomposition:

$$k_{u(mes)} = \max \left\{ 0; \left(1 - \frac{A_a}{\varepsilon k_t k_w \left(k_Y \left(\frac{M_Y(mes)}{\Delta z} \right) + k_o \left(\frac{M_o(mes)}{\Delta z} \right) \right)} \right) \right\} \quad (94)$$

$$k_{u(mic)} = \max \left\{ 0; \left(1 - \frac{A_a}{\varepsilon k_t k_w F_p \left(k_Y \left(\frac{M_Y(mic)}{\Delta z} \right) + k_o \left(\frac{M_o(mic)}{\Delta z} \right) \right)} \right) \right\} \quad (95)$$

where A_a ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$) is a composite microbial parameter that represents a minimum carbon uptake flux that can support an active microbial biomass. Wutzler and Reichstein (2013) showed that this model performs accurately in the long-term, but is not suitable for short-term simulations (e.g. weeks, months) due to the underlying quasi-steady-state assumption.

The source-sink terms T_Y and T_O [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] in equations 87 to 90 are included to account for the mixing of organic matter between pore regions by both tillage and earthworm bioturbation using a simpler modified version of the approach described by Jarvis et al. (2024), which assumes that tillage always results in a net transfer from micropores to mesopores:

$$T_Y = \tau_e (M_Y(mic) - M_Y(mes)) - \Gamma_t k_{till} M_Y(mic) \quad (96)$$

$$T_O = \tau_e (M_O(mic) - M_O(mes)) - \Gamma_t k_{till} M_O(mic) \quad (97)$$

where k_{till} [d^{-1}] is a rate coefficient regulating the transfer of SOM between the two pore regions by tillage. The soil organic matter stored in each of the four pools in USSF also becomes partially mixed and homogenized by tillage across the depth of cultivation.

2.6.1 Organic matter inputs to soil

Equation 87 shows that above-ground crop residues are assumed to enter the young OM pool solely in the mesopore region. Root biomass in USSF is not explicitly partitioned between the pore regions. However, it is reasonable to assume that a smaller proportion of root-derived OM should be input to the micropore region in mechanically stronger soil. Therefore, the fraction of root OM input to the micropores $f_{r(mic)}$ (equations 87 and 89) is expressed as:

$$f_{r(mic)} = \{f_s + w_s(1 - f_s)\} \left(\frac{\phi_{mic}}{\phi_{mes} + \phi_{mic}} \right) \quad (98)$$

where w_s is a weighting factor [-] varying between zero and unity that accounts for the effects of soil mechanical resistance. A fixed proportion of the assimilates allocated below-ground is supplied to the soil as root exudates (see equation 70) and this is distributed to the two young

organic matter pools in soil proportionally with the root biomass in the soil profile (equations 87 and 89). Above-ground crop residues and organic amendments, I_a , are supplied to the young organic matter pool in the mesopore region (see equation 87) as a consequence of incorporation by anecic earthworms as well as by tillage events (see equation 82):

$$I_a = f_{inc(bio)}f_{ret}(k_{res}k_{t(res)}B_{res}) + f_{inc(t)}(\Gamma_t B_{res}) \quad (99)$$

where f_{ret} [-] is a fraction of the residue biomass that is retained and incorporated rather than respired during decomposition, while $f_{inc(bio)}$ [-] and $f_{inc(t)}$ [-] are the proportions of the organic matter that enter a certain soil layer during bio-incorporation and tillage respectively. An exponential function is used to distribute OM by bio-incorporation between the soil surface and a maximum depth of anecic earthworm burrowing z_{max} [m]. Tillage is assumed to distribute the incorporated organic matter uniformly within the depth of cultivation.

3. List of symbols

a	Normalized distance to the root surface for the mean water content	(-)
A	Assimilation rate	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
A_a	Composite parameter governing microbial decomposition	(kg m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)
$A_{bg(d)}$	Below-ground demand for assimilates	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
A_{roots}	Assimilate available for root growth	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
A_{xs}	Nominal cross-sectional area	(m ²)
B_{ag}	Biomass of above-ground residues at harvest	(kg m ⁻²)
B_{crit}	Critical mass of above-ground residues for complete soil cover	(kg m ⁻²)
B_{grain}	Grain biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
$B_{leaf(g)}$	Green leaf biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
$B_{leaf(d)}$	Dead leaf biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
B_{res}	Surface crop residue biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
B_{root}	Root biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
B_{stem}	Stem biomass	(kg m ⁻²)
C	Weighting factor for different kinetic energy in rain and drip	(-)
C_h	Soil thermal capacity	(J m ⁻³ °C ⁻¹)
C_{mac}	Constant affecting saturated macropore hydraulic conductivity	(m ³ d ⁻¹)
C_{max}	Maximum value of weighting factor C	(-)
C_{mat}	Constant determining saturated matrix hydraulic conductivity	(m ³ d ⁻¹)
D	Root diffusion coefficient	(m ² d ⁻¹)
D_{max}	Maximum root diffusion coefficient	(m ² d ⁻¹)
D_{res}	Thermal diffusivity of crop residues	(m ² d ⁻¹)
D_{snow}	Thermal diffusivity of snow	(m ² d ⁻¹)
D_{soil}	Thermal diffusivity of soil	(m ² d ⁻¹)
$E_{r,p}$	Potential evaporation from surface crop residues	(m d ⁻¹)
$E_{s,a}$	Actual soil evaporation	(m d ⁻¹)
$E_{s,p}$	Potential soil evaporation	(m d ⁻¹)
$E_{t,a}$	Actual transpiration	(m d ⁻¹)
$E_{t,p}$	Potential transpiration	(m d ⁻¹)
ET_p	Potential evapotranspiration	(m d ⁻¹)

f_a	Stress function (aeration effect on root growth)	(-)
f_{agg}	Aggregation factor	($m^3 m^{-3}$)
f_{bg}	Fraction of assimilate allocated below-ground	(-)
$f_{bg(max)}$	Maximum fraction of assimilate allocated below-ground	(-)
$f_{bg(max,e)}$	Maximum fraction of assimilate allocated below-ground (early)	(-)
$f_{bg(max,l)}$	Maximum fraction of assimilate allocated below-ground (late)	(-)
f_{clay}	Clay content	($kg kg^{-1}$)
f_{con}	Fraction of macroporosity that is long-range connected	(-)
$f_{con(max)}$	Maximum fraction of long-range connected macroporosity	(-)
f_d	Proportion of the bioporosity destroyed by a tillage event	(-)
f_{ex}	Fraction of below-ground production input to the soil as exudates	(-)
f_{export}	Fraction of crop residues exported at harvest	(-)
f_{grain}	Fraction of assimilate allocated to grain	(-)
$f_{inc(bio)}$	Fraction of bio-incorporated crop residues entering a soil layer	(-)
$f_{inc(bio)}$	Fraction of crop residues entering a soil layer following tillage	(-)
f_{int}	Fraction of incoming radiation/rainfall intercepted by crop canopy	(-)
$f_{int(g)}$	Fraction of incoming radiation intercepted by green leaves	(-)
$f_{int(res)}$	Fraction of incoming radiation intercepted by crop residues	(-)
f_{leaf}	Fraction of assimilate allocated to green leaves	(-)
$f_{leaf(max)}$	Maximum fraction of assimilate allocated to the leaves	(-)
$f_{mic(text)}$	Micropore fraction of the textural pore space	(-)
f_{photo}	Factor for the effect of photoperiod on crop development	(-)
f_r	Fraction of root biomass in a soil layer	(-)
f_{ret}	Retention fraction (crop residue incorporation)	(-)
$f_{r(mic)}$	Fraction of root residues supplied to the micropore region	(-)
f_s	Soil strength factor limiting root growth	(-)
f_{sat}	Moisture response for OM decomposition (value at saturation)	(-)
$f_{sat(mic)}$	Moisture response for OM decomposition (at micropore saturation)	(-)
f_{som}	Soil organic matter content	($kg kg^{-1}$)
$f_{som(c,e)}$	Critical soil organic matter content for endogeic bioturbation	($kg kg^{-1}$)
$f_{som(c,s)}$	Critical soil organic matter content for soil sealing	($kg kg^{-1}$)
$f_{som(m,e)}$	Soil organic matter content for maximum endogeic bioturbation	($kg kg^{-1}$)
$f_{som(n,s)}$	Soil organic matter content above which soil sealing is negligible	($kg kg^{-1}$)
f_{stem}	Fraction of assimilate allocated to stems	(-)
$f_{t(a)}$	Stress function (temperature effect on assimilation)	(-)
f_{tr}	Fraction of senesced leaf biomass translocated to grain	(-)
$f_{t(r)}$	Stress function (temperature effect on root growth)	(-)
$f_{t(s)}$	Stress function (temperature effect on senescence)	(-)
f_{vern}	Vernalization factor for winter-sown crops	(-)
$f_{w(a)}$	Stress function (water stress effect on assimilation)	(-)
$f_{w(s)}$	Stress function (water stress effect on senescence)	(-)
F	Matric flux potential	($m^2 d^{-1}$)
F_o	Matric flux potential at the root surface	($m^2 d^{-1}$)
$F_{o(crit)}$	Critical matric flux potential at the root surface (leaf senescence)	($m^2 d^{-1}$)
F_p	Physical protection factor for SOM decomposition	(-)
GLAI	Green leaf area index	($m^2 m^{-2}$)
h	Height at which canopy drip is generated (= half of crop height)	(m)

h_{max}	Height at which drip velocity reaches terminal velocity	(m)
h_{min}	Height from which canopy drip can cause surface sealing	(m)
I_a	Input of organic matter via above-ground residues	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
I_{cap}	Infiltration capacity	(m d ⁻¹)
I_r	Root decay rate	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
$k_{bio(loss)}$	Rate coefficient for loss of bioporosity	(d ⁻¹)
k_{con}	Rate coefficient for consolidation of tillage pore space	(d ⁻¹)
k_d	Rate coefficient for root decay	(d ⁻¹)
k_h	Thermal conductivity	(J m ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)
k_m	Snowmelt coefficient	(m °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)
k_O	Rate coefficient for decomposition of microbially-processed SOM	(d ⁻¹)
k_{res}	Rate constant for loss of surface residues	(d ⁻¹)
k_{seal}	Rate constant for surface sealing	(cm ⁻¹)
k_{sen}	Rate coefficient for leaf senescence	(d ⁻¹)
$k_{sen(max)}$	Maximum value of rate coefficient for leaf senescence	(d ⁻¹)
$k_{sen(min)}$	Minimum value of rate coefficient for leaf senescence	(d ⁻¹)
$k_{s(max)}$	Maximum value of the sealing rate constant	(cm ⁻¹)
k_t	Temperature response function for SOM decomposition	(-)
k_{till}	Rate coefficient for tillage transfer of SOM between pore regions	(d ⁻¹)
k_{tr}	Rate coefficient for translocation from stem to grain	(d ⁻¹)
$k_{t(res)}$	Temperature response function (crop residue loss)	(d ⁻¹)
$k_{u(mes)}$	Microbial uptake limitation factor (mesopores)	(-)
$k_{u(mic)}$	Microbial uptake limitation factor (micropores)	(-)
k_w	Moisture response function for decomposition of SOM	(-)
k_Y	Rate coefficient for decomposition of particulate SOM	(d ⁻¹)
K	Soil hydraulic conductivity	(m d ⁻¹)
$K_{s(mac)}$	Saturated hydraulic conductivity in the macropore region	(m d ⁻¹)
$K_{s(mat)}$	Saturated hydraulic conductivity in the soil matrix	(m d ⁻¹)
LAI	Total leaf area index	(m ² m ⁻²)
LAI_b	Leaf area index at which Beer's law coefficient is at a minimum	(m ² m ⁻²)
M_{som}	Mass of soil organic matter	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{som(mes)}$	Mass of soil organic matter stored in mesopores	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{som(mic)}$	Mass of soil organic matter stored in micropores	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{Y(mes)}$	Mass of particulate organic matter in mesopore region	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{Y(mic)}$	Mass of particulate organic matter in micropore region	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{O(mes)}$	Mass of microbially-processed organic matter in mesopore region	(kg m ⁻²)
$M_{O(mic)}$	Mass of microbially-processed organic matter in micropore region	(kg m ⁻²)
n_w	Exponent in the moisture response function for SOM decomposition	(-)
p	Slope of the shrinkage characteristic	(-)
P	Precipitation rate	(m d ⁻¹)
$q_{max,r}$	Maximum soil water flow rate towards the root system	(m d ⁻¹)
$q_{max,s}$	Maximum soil water flow rate towards the soil surface	(m d ⁻¹)
q_{UBC}	Net water flow across the soil surface	(m d ⁻¹)
q_0	Infiltration rate	(m d ⁻¹)
Q	Soil penetration resistance	(kPa)
Q_{lim}	Limiting soil penetration resistance that stops root penetration	(kPa)
Q_{opt}	Upper limit value for optimal soil penetration resistance	(kPa)

r_m	Average half distance to the root surface	(m)
r_o	Root radius	(m)
r_s	Shrinkage geometry factor	(-)
R	Rainfall rate	(m d ⁻¹)
$R_{bg(pot)}$	First-order rate coefficient for potential root growth	(d ⁻¹)
R_{ET}	Extra-terrestrial radiation	(MJ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
R_{LD}	Effective root length density	(m m ⁻³)
R_s	Incoming solar radiation	(MJ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
RUE_{max}	Maximum radiation use efficiency	(kg MJ ⁻¹)
S_d	Crop development stage	(-)
S_{d1}	End of first crop development stage	(-)
S_{d2}	End of second crop development stage	(-)
S_{d3}	End of third crop development stage	(-)
S_{d4}	End of fourth crop development stage	(-)
S_f	Snowfall	(m d ⁻¹)
S_{leaf}	Specific leaf area	(m ² kg ⁻¹)
S_m	Snowmelt	(m d ⁻¹)
S_{root}	Specific root length	(m kg ⁻¹)
t	Time	(d)
T	Current air temperature	(°C)
T_{av}	Mean daily air temperature	(°C)
T_{cap}	Ceiling air temperature for temperature sum calculations	(°C)
T_f	Threshold air temperature for snowfall	(°C)
T_m	Threshold air temperature for snowmelt	(°C)
$T_{o(low)}$	Air temperature defining optimum range for assimilation	(°C)
$T_{o(high)}$	Air temperature defining optimum range for assimilation	(°C)
T_b	Base air temperature	(°C)
T_c	Ceiling air temperature	(°C)
T_{max}	Maximum daily air temperature	(°C)
T_{min}	Minimum daily air temperature	(°C)
$T_{opt(res)}$	Optimum temperature for loss of surface crop residues	(°C)
T_{ref}	Reference soil temperature for SOM decomposition	(°C)
T_s	Soil temperature	(°C)
$T_{s,1}$	Temperature at the mid-point of the uppermost soil layer	(°C)
T_{sum}	Temperature sum	(°C)
$T_{sum(e)}$	Temperature sum required for emergence	(°C)
$T_{sum(a)}$	Temperature sum required for anthesis	(°C)
$T_{sum(m)}$	Temperature sum required for maturity	(°C)
T_{surf}	Soil surface temperature	(°C)
T_O	Source-sink term for transfer of old SOM between pore regions	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
T_Y	Source-sink term for transfer of young SOM between pore regions	(kg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
T_0	Minimum soil temperature at which SOM decomposition occurs	(°C)
U	Water uptake rate from a soil layer	(m ³ m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)
V_{bio}	Volume of soil biopores	(m ³)
V_{crack}	Volume of cracks	(m ³)
V_{mat}	Volume of matrix pore space	(m ³)
$V_{mat(ref)}$	Reference matrix pore volume when fully swollen	(m ³)

V_p	Total volume of soil pore space	(m ³)
V_s	Volume of soil solids	(m ³)
V_{sta}	Volume of static macropores	(m ³)
V_{till}	Volume of tillage voids	(m ³)
V_t	Total soil volume	(m ³)
V_w	Volume of water	(m ³)
w_{min}	Weighted heat capacity of the soil solids	(J m ⁻³ °C ⁻¹)
w_s	Weighting factor	(-)
Z	Height in soil profile	(m)
Z_{max}	Maximum depth of anecic earthworm burrowing	(m)
Z_{res}	Thickness of surface crop residues	(m)
Z_{snow}	Thickness of snowpack	(m)
z^*	Proportion of a soil layer included within the cultivated layer	(-)
α_{bio}	Rate constant for bioporosity formation due to surface residue	(m ³ m ⁻³ d ⁻¹ (kg m ⁻²) ⁻¹)
β	Extinction coefficient in Beers law	(-)
β_1	Extinction coefficient in Beers law at crop emergence	(-)
β_2	Extinction coefficient in Beers law at LAI _b	(-)
ε	Microbial efficiency (organic matter retention coefficient)	(-)
$\varepsilon_{r(max)}$	Maximum effective root fraction	(-)
ϕ	Total porosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{bio}	Bioporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{crack}	Crack porosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{mac}	Macroporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
$\phi_{mac(p)}$	Percolating macroporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
$\phi_{mac(t)}$	Threshold macroporosity for percolation	(m ³ m ⁻³)
$\phi_{mac(u)}$	Macroporosity at maximum connected fraction	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{mat}	Matrix porosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{mes}	Mesoporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{mic}	Microporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{ref}	Reference matrix porosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{sta}	Permanent macroporosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ϕ_{till}	Tillage porosity	(m ³ m ⁻³)
γ_{min}	Density of soil mineral matter	(kg m ⁻³)
γ_{som}	Density of soil organic matter	(kg m ⁻³)
λ_{mac}	Pore size distribution index for macropore region	(-)
λ_{mat}	Pore size distribution index in the soil matrix	(-)
$\lambda_{mat(t)}$	Pore size distribution index for non-structured soil matrix	(-)
λ_{vap}	Latent heat of vapourization	(MJ kg ⁻¹)
θ	Soil water content	(m ³ m ⁻³)
θ_a	Soil air content	(m ³ m ⁻³)
$\theta_{a(crit)}$	Critical soil air content	(m ³ m ⁻³)
θ_{crit}	Critical water content for percolating water phase	(m ³ m ⁻³)
θ_w	Wilting point	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ρ_r	Tissue (bulk) density of roots	(kg m ⁻³)
ρ_b	Soil bulk density	(kg m ⁻³)

ρ_{res}	Bulk density of surface crop residues	(kg m ⁻³)
ζ	Composite root parameter	(m ⁻²)
τ	Tortuosity/connectivity factor in the soil matrix	(-)
τ_a	Soil turnover rate due to anecic earthworms	(d ⁻¹)
$\tau_{a,0}$	Minimum rate of bioporosity generation	(m ³ m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)
τ_e	Soil turnover rate due to endogeic earthworms	(d ⁻¹)
$\tau_{e(max)}$	Maximum soil turnover rate due to endogeic earthworms	(d ⁻¹)
τ_{till}	Gain of porosity due to a tillage event	(m ³ m ⁻³)
ψ	Soil water pressure head	(m)
ψ_{max}	Soil water pressure head equivalent to the largest soil pore	(m)
$\psi_{mes/mac}$	Soil water pressure head corresponding to the largest mesopore	(m)
$\psi_{mic/mes}$	Soil water pressure head corresponding to the largest micropore	(m)
ψ_w	Soil water pressure head at wilting point	(m)
Δz	Soil layer thickness	(m)
Δz_{ref}	Reference thickness of the soil layer	(m)
Δz_1	Thickness of the uppermost soil layer	(m)
Γ_{d1}	Binary variable to indicate if crop stage d1 has been reached	(-)
Γ_{d2}	Binary variable to indicate if crop stage d2 has been reached	(-)
Γ_{d3}	Binary variable to indicate if crop stage d3 has been reached	(-)
Γ_h	Binary variable to indicate day of harvest	(-)
Γ_t	Binary variable to indicate day of tillage	(-)
Γ_o	Binary variable to indicate the uppermost soil layer	(-)
Γ_w	Binary variable to indicate a wetted soil surface	(-)

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The development of the USSF model was initiated in 2018 in a one-year project funded by the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS; grant number 2018-02319). Further model developments and applications were funded by two EU EJP SOIL projects *MaxRootC* (“Optimizing roots for sustainable crop production in Europe – pure cultures and cover crops”) and *SoilX* (“Soil management to mitigate climate-change related precipitation extremes”) under the H2020 Grant agreement number 862695.

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